

COOPERATION BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND CASPIAN REGION STATES IN THE TRANSPORT AND TRANSIT SECTOR

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Abstract. This article examines the transport and transit sector as a key area of cooperation between Uzbekistan and the Caspian region states. The study explores the strategic aspects of Uzbekistan's foreign policy engagement with Caspian states, emphasizing the importance of transport infrastructure and logistics in diversifying export routes, enhancing economic independence, and integrating the country into the global economy. The article analyzes Uzbekistan's efforts to improve transit potential through multimodal routes, strengthen regional cooperation, and implement initiatives aimed at creating a sustainable transport system.

Keywords. Caspian region, transport and transit cooperation, Uzbekistan, international transport corridors, Middle Corridor, Caspian Sea ports, transit potential.

Uzbekistan's foreign policy toward the Caspian region is shaped by several factors, including ensuring national interests, strengthening regional cooperation, utilizing transport and logistics opportunities, and participating in international energy and infrastructure projects. Uzbekistan's approaches to interaction with Caspian states are based on principles of mutual respect, equality, and pragmatism, enabling the country to effectively adapt to the challenges and trends of the modern international order. For Uzbekistan, as a landlocked country, cooperation with Caspian region states is of strategic importance. It enables the republic to integrate into global transport and logistics chains, diversify export routes, and strengthen its economic independence.

In the joint statement by the President of Turkmenistan, S. Berdimuhamedov, and the President of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, the importance of interconnection and unity between the issues of ensuring international peace, security, and sustainable development in Central Asia and the Caspian region was emphasized.[1] The leaders of the two countries expressed their support for Turkmenistan's initiative to establish a Zone of Peace, Trust, and Cooperation "Central Asia–Caspian Region," noting the significance of this model as a platform for promoting ideas aimed at developing multilateral interaction in the interests of global peace and sustainable development. The creation of such a zone provides unique opportunities for implementing projects focused on the development of transport corridors, logistics infrastructure, and the expansion of interregional trade. This idea establishes a platform for integrating the efforts of Caspian states and Central Asian countries to ensure long-term peace, security, and sustainable development. Furthermore, the formation of the Zone of Peace and Trust will create favorable conditions for deepening trade and economic cooperation. The development of transport corridors such as TRACECA and North-South will significantly reduce logistics costs, thereby boosting mutual trade between the regions.

As part of implementing the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy, emphasis is placed on strengthening transit potential, creating "green corridors" to simplify foreign trade operations, and increasing the volume of transit freight transportation.[2] The primary focus is on modernizing transport infrastructure, improving logistics chains, and introducing modern digital

solutions to accelerate and optimize processes. These measures aim to enhance Uzbekistan's competitiveness as a key transit hub in the region and create favorable conditions for expanding international trade.

One of the tools for achieving these objectives is the development of multimodal freight transportation along the "North-South" route. The Caspian region plays a strategic role in the transport chain of the "North-South" route, providing direct access to international maritime routes through the ports of Azerbaijan, Iran, Russia, and Kazakhstan. For Uzbekistan, this route offers alternative opportunities for transporting goods, bypassing congested and more expensive traditional routes, such as the Suez Canal. Utilizing the Caspian region as a logistics hub enables multimodal transportation by combining rail, road, and sea transport. This integration of transport modes helps reduce delivery times, minimize transportation costs, and increase transit cargo flows through Uzbekistan.

In November 2023, the Ministries of Transport of Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Russia signed a Memorandum of Understanding aimed at the creation and development of an international multimodal transport corridor "Russia – Caspian Sea – Turkmenistan – Uzbekistan – Kyrgyzstan." [3] The establishment and development of this corridor are of great importance to the participating countries, particularly Uzbekistan, given its strategic geographical location. Such a corridor has the potential to become a powerful driver for regional cooperation, economic growth, and the enhancement of transport infrastructure competitiveness.

Central Asia, situated at the crossroads of major trade routes between Europe and Asia, possesses significant transit potential. However, its full realization is constrained by underdeveloped transport infrastructure and the lack of a coordinated logistics strategy. The new transport corridor connecting Russia, the Caspian Sea, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan provides a foundation for integrating existing transport networks and increasing freight volumes. The corridor offers participating countries direct access to Caspian Sea ports and, in the future, to international maritime routes. This minimizes transportation costs and reduces delivery times, which is particularly crucial for export-oriented economies like Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan is actively expanding its non-resource exports, including agricultural products, textiles, chemicals, and construction materials. The corridor offers a shorter and more cost-effective route to external markets, enhancing the competitiveness of Uzbek products. According to our forecasts, the volume of freight transported through the new corridor could increase by 30-40% in its first years of operation. This will have a positive impact on the revenues of transport companies and the development of Uzbekistan's railway and road infrastructure. [4]

Uzbekistan plans to actively utilize the ports of Caspian states, such as Aktau and Turkmenbashi, for the export and import of goods. Joint projects with Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan are being implemented to establish logistics centers and improve port infrastructure, which will help reduce delivery times and costs. In November 2024, a delegation from Uzbekistan held negotiations with the National Company "Aktau Sea Commercial Port" on organizing exports via the Caspian Sea. Following the meeting, an agreement was signed to cooperate and implement joint projects aimed at developing container transportation and goods transit. [5]

The International Sea Port of Turkmenbashi holds significant potential for strengthening Uzbekistan's economic position in the Caspian Sea region. Utilizing this port as a key transportation artery opens new opportunities for Uzbekistan to expand exports, develop logistics, and integrate into international trade chains. Active cooperation with the Turkmenbashi port can greatly influence the country's economic development.

Firstly, the Turkmenbashi port can become a strategic link for diversifying Uzbekistan's export routes. Amid increasing competition for transport corridors and geopolitical challenges, using the Caspian region as a logistics hub enables Uzbekistan to reduce dependence on traditional routes. This is particularly important as access to maritime routes ensures more stable and predictable supplies to markets in Europe, the Middle East, and South Asia.

Secondly, the Turkmenbashi port can improve the transportation efficiency of Uzbek goods. Developing container transportation through the Caspian Sea, using modern logistics standards, reduces transportation costs and improves delivery times. This is especially critical for Uzbekistan's export products such as cotton, textiles, chemical goods, and fresh fruits and vegetables, which require swift and careful transportation.

Moreover, strengthening cooperation with the Turkmenbashi port supports the development of Uzbekistan's economic diplomacy. Implementing joint transport projects with Turkmenistan enhances regional cooperation and establishes a foundation for long-term economic partnerships. This aligns with Uzbekistan's strategic priorities to create a favorable investment climate and attract foreign investors interested in accessing the growing markets of Central Asia.

Particular attention is also being paid to the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route, which connects Central Asia with Turkey and Europe. The TransCaspian International Transport Route, also known as the "Middle Corridor," is a key direction for cargo transportation between China, Central Asia, the Caspian region, the Caucasus, Turkey, and Europe. The Trans-Caspian International Transport Route includes several key seaports such as Baku (Azerbaijan), Astara, Lankaran, and Sumgait. This route is becoming increasingly in demand amid geopolitical changes and growing demand for transport services, serving as an alternative to traditional routes. In 2023, the volume of cargo transported via the Middle Corridor reached approximately 2.7 million tons, representing a 20% increase compared to the previous year.[6]

Currently, Uzbekistan and Azerbaijan are actively working on the establishment of a joint venture aimed at modernizing logistics along the Middle Corridor. The primary goal of this project is to improve the quality of transport services, increase the route's capacity, and reduce cargo delivery times. The Middle Corridor plays a strategic role in ensuring transport links between Europe and Asia, making its development a priority for both countries. To achieve these objectives, the parties plan to implement a series of measures in the field of transport infrastructure.[7] Key focus areas include the construction of new ferries for cargo transportation across the Caspian Sea, the development of modern warehouse complexes, and the implementation of digital technologies and electronic document management systems. These measures will significantly enhance the efficiency of logistics processes, reduce cargo handling times, and strengthen the route's competitiveness on the international stage.

Uzbekistan also plans to increase cargo transportation volumes to European Union countries through Bulgaria, utilizing the capabilities of the Middle Corridor.[8] This route allows for the optimization of logistics by reducing delivery times and transportation costs, making it one of the key directions for the development of export-import operations. Uzbekistan intends to actively leverage the potential of Bulgarian ports and transport infrastructure to strengthen trade and economic ties with Europe.

Bulgaria, with its advantageous geographic location and developed port network, serves as an important link between Central Asia and the European Union.

A key advantage of this route is its multimodality, incorporating rail, sea, and road transportation, which enhances the flexibility and reliability of logistics operations. Furthermore, the use of Bulgarian ports such as Burgas and Varna promotes the development of trade flows through the Black Sea, creating new opportunities for exporting Uzbek products, including agricultural and industrial goods.

The Organization of Turkic States (OTS) serves as a key platform for deepening multilateral cooperation among the countries of the Turkic world, including Uzbekistan, which became a full-fledged member in 2019.[9] Uzbekistan's accession to the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) has opened new prospects in the fields of economic, cultural, political, and scientific cooperation, aligning with the country's national interests and its foreign policy strategy aimed at fostering regional cooperation. With its significant economic and demographic potential, Uzbekistan plays a crucial role within the OTS structure, contributing to the implementation of

major initiatives within the organization. The country's membership in the OTS reflects its aspiration to strengthen ties with the Turkic community, integrate into regional economic and logistical chains, and enhance its influence on the international stage.

The construction of the "China-Kyrgyzstan–Uzbekistan" railway will begin on December 27, 2024, marking an important milestone in the implementation of one of the key infrastructure projects in the region.[10] This large-scale project will serve as the foundation for strengthening transport connectivity between Central Asian countries, China, and other regions, creating new opportunities for trade, logistics, and regional integration. The launch of this corridor will enhance trade relations and open new markets while simultaneously reducing transportation costs and increasing the competitiveness of products from the participating countries. Additionally, the railway will form part of the Middle Corridor, playing a key role in the TransCaspian International Transport Route, which passes through Kazakhstan, the Caspian Sea, Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Turkey, linking China with Europe.

Overall, effective cooperation in the transport and transit sector within the framework of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) offers significant opportunities for Uzbekistan. It will allow the country to strengthen its position as a strategically important logistics hub in Central Asia, providing access to key transport routes connecting Europe, the Middle East, and Asia.

Uzbekistan Supports Azerbaijan's Initiative to Implement the Zangezur Corridor Project.[11] The Zangezur Corridor is a significant infrastructure project that plays a strategic role in shaping a new transport and logistics architecture in the Eurasian region. Its implementation has the potential to become a key link in integrating the transport systems of Central Asia, the Caucasus, and Europe, providing more efficient and faster cargo transportation.

The Zangezur Corridor is a strategically important route connecting Azerbaijan with the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Spanning 43 kilometers, the corridor begins at the border crossing in Nakhchivan and passes through Azerbaijani territory. Along its route are four major cities with a total population of 392,000 people. For Azerbaijan, the Zangezur Corridor plays a strategic role in the country's long-term economic and geopolitical outlook. This route not only promotes the integration of internal territories but also strengthens the country's position as a key logistics hub in Eurasia.

Initially, the Zangezur Corridor was envisioned to promote the development of rail and road connections between Russia and Turkey through Azerbaijan's and Armenia's transit potential, stimulating trade growth. The project was also seen as the economic foundation of the "3+3" platform, proposed by Azerbaijan and Turkey and supported by Russia, aimed at creating a regional geo-economic space free from external influence. However, the corridor's implementation has raised concerns in Armenia and Iran, while Georgia remains distant, citing unresolved issues in its relations with Russia.[12]

Uzbekistan's participation in the project will enable the country to strengthen its position as a regional transit hub. According to initial estimates, the Zangezur Corridor is expected to handle the transportation of 5 to 10 million tons of cargo. Its advantage lies in its favorable geographic location: the route traverses relatively flat

terrain, unlike mountainous alternatives, allowing for increased cargo volumes and reduced delivery times.[13] According to forecasts, the launch of the Zangezur Corridor will reduce cargo delivery times from Uzbekistan to European and Caucasian markets by 20–30%, leading to lower transportation costs and increased competitiveness of Uzbek products on the international stage.

Iran and Uzbekistan are two of the largest countries in the region, and accordingly, they face the important task of establishing regional peace and stability.[14] According to Iranian expert F. Bonesh, in December 1991, Iran was among the first countries to recognize Uzbekistan's independence, and diplomatic relations between the two states were established in May 1992. However, despite official meetings, the development of relations between Iran and Uzbekistan

over the following two and a half decades faced several obstacles. In fact, until 2016, ties between the two countries did not reach a high level and were not marked by notable achievements. After Shavkat Mirziyoyev came to power in Uzbekistan, the country gradually began implementing a foreign policy of "reducing tensions," "open doors," and "balancing relations with regional powers." This policy shift was incorporated into Uzbekistan's foreign agenda and led to a transformation in relations with Iran, moving them towards improvement. Significant steps in this process included an increase in meetings, a visit to the port of Chabahar, the activation of the Joint Economic Commission's work, the signing of transit agreements, and Uzbekistan's readiness to join the Chabahar Agreement project.[15]

Uzbekistan has expressed interest in consistently and effectively expanding cooperation with Iran in several key areas. Priority sectors for interaction include political, trade and economic, transport and communication, and cultural and humanitarian spheres, each of which holds strategic importance for strengthening bilateral relations.[16]

On June 18, 2023, a meeting took place in Tehran between the Leader of the Islamic Revolution, Ayatollah Seyyed Ali Khamenei, and the President of

Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Both sides expressed mutual interest in deepening cooperation in various areas, emphasizing the historical, cultural, and scientific ties between the two countries. Ayatollah Khamenei highlighted the importance of reviving bilateral relations, noting the limitations of past interactions. During the talks, prospects for strengthening trade ties were discussed, including achieving an annual trade turnover of \$1 billion. Particular attention was given to the development of infrastructure and the improvement of customs procedures to stimulate mutual trade. The role of Iran in providing Uzbekistan access to the global ocean through Turkmenistan and Afghanistan was also emphasized, opening new opportunities for trade and transport.[17] This meeting marked an important step toward strengthening bilateral relations, laying the groundwork for further cooperation in political, economic, and cultural spheres.

In 2022, Uzbekistan signed an agreement granting the country access to the port of Chabahar, located in Iran's southeastern province.[18] The purpose of the agreement is to establish a new transport corridor for cargo transportation between Afghanistan, India, and Iran via the Iranian port of Chabahar. By linking the Chabahar transit road with the Caucasus and Eastern European countries, Iran offers an alternative to the maritime route through the Suez Canal. Located in southeastern Iran, in the province of Sistan and Baluchistan, the port of Chabahar holds a strategically important position within the system of international transport and trade corridors. Its unique geographical location on the coast of the Gulf of Oman provides direct access to international maritime routes, making it a key logistical hub for Central Asia, South Asia, the Caucasus, and Eastern Europe. In the context of globalization and the growing interdependence of nations, Chabahar is increasingly significant for establishing sustainable economic ties and diversifying transport routes. One of Chabahar's key characteristics is its ability to serve as an alternative to traditional maritime routes, including the Suez Canal.

The Trans-Afghan Corridor includes key projects such as the construction of the "Termez–Mazar-i-Sharif–Kabul–Peshawar" railway.[18] This route will serve as a vital link connecting Central Asia with Pakistan and India, providing access to the ports of Gwadar and Karachi on the Arabian Sea coast. For Uzbekistan, this translates into reduced transportation costs, increased export volumes, and access to a broader consumer base in South Asia, including India's population of over one billion. The corridor can become part of a broader network of transport routes, integrating with initiatives like the "Belt and Road" and connecting to the infrastructure of the Middle Corridor and the Trans-Caspian route. This integration will combine the capabilities of various regional initiatives, ensuring a synergistic effect.

Uzbekistan's initiative to create a new multimodal transport corridor connecting Turkey, the Caucasus, Central Asia, and South Asia through Afghanistan is also significant.[19] This

initiative is of particular importance in the context of strengthening transport and logistics connectivity in the region, as well as ensuring sustainable economic growth. The multimodal corridor through Afghanistan has the potential to become an important element of transport infrastructure, linking regions with varying levels of economic development and contributing to their integration into global supply chains.

Overall, Uzbekistan's cooperation with the Caspian region states in the transport and transit sphere is a strategically important direction in the country's foreign policy. The development of international transport corridors, such as the "North-South," TRACECA, and the Middle Corridor, strengthens Uzbekistan's economic ties with Europe, the Middle East, and South Asia. The use of Caspian Sea ports, including Aktau, Turkmenbashi, and Baku, opens new opportunities for diversifying export routes, reducing logistics costs, and increasing transit freight volumes.

The implementation of multimodal transport projects is of particular significance, as they allow for the efficient combination of rail, road, and sea transport. This reduces transportation costs, minimizes delivery times, and increases the competitiveness of Uzbek products on international markets. Joint projects with Caspian states, including the creation of logistics centers and infrastructure modernization, strengthen Uzbekistan's position as a key transit hub in Central Asia.

An important element of strengthening regional cooperation is Uzbekistan's participation in initiatives such as the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route, which connects Central Asia with Europe via the Caucasus. These projects contribute to the region's integration into global logistics chains, enhance investment attractiveness, and ensure sustainable development. Thus, transport and transit cooperation with the Caspian region states is not only an important tool for strengthening Uzbekistan's economic diplomacy but also a strategic factor in enhancing its competitiveness in the international trade system. The successful implementation of these initiatives will promote long-term economic growth, deepen regional cooperation, and form a sustainable transport infrastructure that meets modern challenges.

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